

E-HRM: A Conceptual Review

Dr. Sonali Saha¹, Dr. Amol Gawande², Muskan Sharma³

¹Associate Professor, Dr. D. Y. Patil B-School, Pune, Maharashtra, India

²Professor, Global Business School and Research Centre, Pune, Maharashtra, India

³Student, Dr. D. Y. Patil B-School, Pune, Maharashtra, India

ABSTRACT

E-HRM uses Information Technology for Human Resource practices that enable easy interactions between employers and employees. It stores information regarding employee personal data, payroll, training, performance management, recruitment, and strategic orientation. As levels of computerization have increased, several service functions have been benefited. For instance, accounting is one area where substantial changes have taken place with IT initiatives' help. Similarly, HRM is another service function injected with a number of IT initiatives to make it more efficient and effective. This paper carries a conceptual review of E-HRM, looking at its meaning, definition, advantages, and disadvantages.

Keywords: E-HRM, IT, HRM

INTRODUCTION

Over the past decades, the personnel department's role has been changed from that of an administrator to, more recently, a critical component in the business's competitive achievement. Companies have now started to embrace a "human capital approach," one that considers the money spent cultivating innovation in the workforce as an investment. Just as the role of Human Resources keeps on changing, technology has continued to evolve. If Human Resources' role has consistently been to convey the workforce support and management based on the requirements of the business, then technology's role has been that of an enabler. Companies are utilizing human capital technologies for use by everybody in the business.

Electronic- Human Resource Management (E-HRM) is a web-based solution that exploits the latest web application technology to convey an online real-time Human Resource Management Solution (Gowan Mary, 2001). There is a major distinction between HRIS (Human Resource Information Systems) and E-HRM in that HRIS are coordinated towards the HR department itself. With E-HRM, the target group is the HR staff and individuals outside this department: the employees and management. Technically speaking, E-HRM is the technical unlocking of HRIS for all employees of an organization. Wright and Dyer differentiate three HRM areas where organizations can decide to 'offer' HR services face-to-face or through an electronic means: traditional HRM, transactional HRM, and transformational HRM (Wright P. M et al., 2000). E-HRM is a method of actualizing HR strategies, policies, and practices in organizations through the cognizant and coordinated help of and/or with the full utilization of web technology-based channels (Ruel H. et al., 2004). The results of the observational examination by Ravarini et al. (2019) show that the applied structure empowers the advancement of a Hellenic association, and they feature that, to manage such turn of events, a focal job is played by electronic, human resource management (e-HRM), characterized as far as HRM measures, programming stages, and hierarchical culture. Ahmed et al. (2019) reveal insight into the idea of Human Resource executives. In that, the authors have endeavored to underline a portion of the significant advancements in HRM. The article explains the development from HRM to E-HRM and why it is getting unavoidable for organizations to comprehend and acknowledge it. The conversation likewise features nitty-gritty clarification of the highlights and prospects of E-HRM and its uniqueness in correlation with conventional HRM practices. In summary, the article likewise explains HRM as a vital idea while focusing on identifying components with innovative supremacy. The article helps people excited to lead academic work in the area of E-HRM and its key significance in the years to come.

As is the case with all new systems and concepts, E-HRM accompanies its own set of challenges and issues that require cautious scrutiny before being adopted and propelled in any organization.

Meaning of E-HRM

Processing & transmission of digitized HR information is called E-HRM or Electronic Human Resource Management.

E-HRM is applying IT for HR practices, which empowers easy interactions between the employee and employers. It stores data regarding payroll, performance management, employee personal data, recruitment, training, and strategic orientation.

Definition of E-HRM

E-HRM has been defined as “a way of implementing HR strategies, policies and practices in organizations through a conscious and directed support of and/or with the full use of web-technology-based channels” or more recently, and more extensively, as “the planning, implementation, and application of information systems for both networking and supporting actors in their shared performing of HR activities.”

Evolution of E-HRM

HR functions started almost 90 years back when the first HR department was established in 1920. From that point forward, there have been constant improvements and development in this discipline. Functions of HR have extended over the past decades from record-keeping to involvement as a strategic partner.

The evolution of HR began with the Industrial revolution. The industrial revolution affected the practices used to control the workers. It was during this time; HR theories began developing. Increment in production prompted an expansion in the workforce and required more new policies to be embraced by managers to regulate the working environment. With an expansion in jobs, new job descriptions and specifications were developed.

As of now, in 1903, the first concept of HRM was established as scientific management by Frederick Winslow Taylor, which portrayed workers as machines, and the social aspect of human behavior was left unnoticed. As indicated by, scientific management concepts clarified-

1. Workers should be motivated to follow the procedures.
2. Workers have to match physically and mentally with the job.

The social aspect which was left unnoticed was acknowledged in the late 1920s and early 1930s during Hawthorne studies. With additionally enlarging in research areas of HR, the era of behavioral sciences developed. During this period, the visualization of the organization was changed. Employees & organizations were not considered as separate entities; however, together as an organization.

Behavioral applied science frames the basis for today's human resource and organizational behavior. It was during the 1920s, the concept of scientific management was moved to personnel management.

Experts were hired to keep the records, keep up payroll systems and look into other concerns related to employees. With the improvement in technology, economics, and workforce, the moving of personnel management to HRM started between 1960 and 1970, and from that point forward, HRM's term is widely accepted, adopted, and utilized all over the world.

Presently, the organizations had a formal HR department with people experts in the HR discipline. With time, businesses turned out to be more globalized. The changes in the business environment changed quickly, demanding stronger, effective HR practices. More pressure fell on HR professionals from multiple stakeholders, customers and competitors. During the 1980s, organizations realized that a competitive edge could be accomplished from their internal factors, especially human resources. This prompts the rise of a new discipline named “Strategic HRM.”

Under strategic management, it was recognized that human capital as an internal resource could assist the firms to create value, which was rare and hard to imitate, whereas external factors like natural resources, technology, and economies of scale can easily be replicated.

With this change of HRM to Strategic HRM, researchers and academicians started to depict how HR can play a strategic role in contribution to OE and thus, clarifying the relationship between HRM and OE through different models.

The HR researchers recognized and justified the role of HRM in the organization. The connection between HRM practices and OE was perceived and acknowledged. HRM was the researchers' favourite topic for depicting its alignment with the organization's mission, vision, and strategies. It turned into a strategic player in its contribution to OE.

Sustainability was another element added to the tasks of HRM. In today's dynamic changing environment, sustainability is the most wanted element for all organizations. To accomplish sustainability, it needs to be out in the center of organizational strategy.

There is a need to consolidate an environment within the organization which prompts sustainability. Senior management needs to help the HRM department in making a sustainable environment. All departments need to be integrated completely as it influences all in the organization.

To make the process flow quicker and smoother, the introduction of technology in the organization is significant. Technology developments can play a major role in contributing to OE and sustainability. With the approach of technology, HR functions will turn out to be more digitalized. All processes were bolstered by technology. Now, HRM has become e-HRM.

E-HRM was developed with the objective to accomplish high competencies, high commitment, higher congruence, and cost-effectiveness for an organization towards a sustainable society.

Information and communication technologies (ICT) help firms process, integrate, communicate, and get all information within organizations through the intranet, keeping flawless the confidential information's protection and security.

This new state of technology will engage and urge HRM to step ahead towards a sustainable society.

The recent surge in E-HRM

Right skilling sets out an opportunity to fill the gaps between employee performance, skill, and organization performance necessities. Sorouh coined the right skilling term. It is better than scaling down of the companies. It is a collective effort of employers and employees. It includes retraining of employees at their workplace to perform better. It improves productivity, makes employees loyal, and gives new learning to employees. E-retirement includes pension calculators on the company's websites and also gives E-solutions for EPF and Gratuity. It creates a fair amount of pension for the employees as per company norms. It likewise encourages E-delivery of pension. E-learning includes broad use of computers, laptops, mobiles, tabs. It is a prevailing trend of the current corporate education environment.

TEL, IBT, CBT, WBT, VLE, etc., are the forms of E-learning. It is good for working professionals, global education, and individuals who are unable to approach college. In these blogs, webcams, chat boxes are normally utilized. E-recruitment includes recruiting prospective employees through job portals like Naukri, Monster, Shine, Wisdom, etc. Nowadays, it is a rising business as companies used to outsource their recruitment process to recruitment firms. Work-life balance includes a balance between employees' work and lifestyle to maintain equilibrium with health, pleasure, family, development, and work schedules and stress. Its motive is to create ideal employees who can contribute extra roles & behaviors to the organizations. Ideal employees prove to be a valuable asset for the companies likewise infuses success into the organization. Green HRM plays a pivotal role in protecting the environment from man-made disasters by making awareness among employees. It likewise spurs them to reduce carbon footprints and other pollution instigating activities to maintain and upgrade the ecological balance and beauty of nature and our planet earth. It is typically done through the utilization of eco-friendly products, pollution control, waste management, etc.

Advantages of E-HRM

E-HRM is not suitable for organizations where employees are not prepared to accept or utilize it. Major benefits/advantages of E-HRM are as follows:

- Ensuring efficient services at an amazing speed.
- Improving quality services.
- Helping the reduction of costly time and labor.
- Facilitating routine tasks like maintaining the portfolio, record keeping, collecting and storing relevant data regarding the human resource.
- Making, reporting, and analyzing data quickly.
- Improving accuracy and reducing human bias.
- Handling bundles of employee data from multiple locations fairly and quickly.
- Benefiting everyone through standardization and automation.
- Playing decisive roles towards a paperless office.
- Performing crucial HRM functions such as recruitment, selection, training, and development by utilizing web-based technology.
- Maintaining anonymity of staff in evaluation/feedback giving.

Disadvantages of E-HRM

Disadvantages/limitations of E-HRM are listed below:

- It is not easy to maintain the confidentiality of the input data.
- It involves a high cost to maintain and implement E-HRM.
- Electronic media are vulnerable, which might be assaulted by viruses from anyplace on the Internet. Contracting a virus can disable your HR management system seriously enough to render it unusable for an indeterminate time. E-HRM is subject to corruption, data losses, or hacking.
- Computers and their associated programs are only as powerful as their human users; data entry errors can and do happen. In HR management systems, such errors can have grave consequences.
- Organizations need to contribute more to training and development before embracing e- HRM.

CONCLUSION

HRM has fast evolved into EHRM. Organizations that have been able to implement EHRM successfully have reaped significant benefits. A number of operational areas in the HRM function like personal data, payroll, training, performance management, recruitment, and others have become computerized, which has increased the efficiency and effectiveness of the HRM function. Those lagging should take immediate steps to shift to EHRM from manual systems. Even though there are some disadvantages of EHRM, the benefits of EHRM in the long-run far outweigh its initial costs and investments. The recent surge in EHRM is evidence of the growing realization across organizations of the benefits of EHRM.

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